

IMPORTANCE OF COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

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In this article is discussed about paying attention to the effective teaching of speech activities in foreign language teaching. Information about the emergence of the competence-based approach, its importance and role in improving the types of speech activity is given.

Key words; student, types of speech activity, competence-based approach, approach, improvement

According to the analytical opinions of scientists, low stage of communicative competence in learning a foreign language, intercultural disparity hinders the full acquisition of the language. In this regard, the main goal of teaching a foreign language is to form "types of speech activity" in students, that is, knowledge related to everyday, scientific and professional activities.

Foreign languages integrated language skills, oral speech practice (listening and speaking), written speech practice, communicative grammar, communicative lexicon (vocabulary increase), discourse (text) analysis, English is studied as an international communication language as independent learning skills, current problems of the field, professional ethics, development of intercultural communication competence, written communication in business, history and directions of the studied specialty, current problems of the field, professional ethics, development of intercultural communication. business it is required to have sufficient knowledge and skills in written communication, the history and directions of the studied specialty. Finding a solution to the problems that arise at the same time and ensuring the quality of the result is a somewhat complicated process. In order to achieve easier and faster results in this process, we chose to focus on the process of improving the "types of speech activity" based on the competence approach to the students who are studying, in order to better convey the topic during the training.

The analysis of many literatures and scientific studies shows that the problems of communication organization are of constant interest in the field of teaching foreign languages. The reason for this is explained by different circumstances. The first obstacle that appears above all is the ability of students to learn differently, information is learned at different levels at the same time,

and it is shown that students have different character and temperament (physical and psychological state). Researchers emphasize that high potential is necessary for successful teaching results. It is not without benefit to provide the students' communicative abilities, the quality of their speech and the correctness of their speech with clear, clear, impressive, logical, interesting arguments through the possibility of using interactive teaching methods in foreign language acquisition.

Formation of teaching in higher education institutions on the basis of various strategies is important. At the same time, alternative methodological solutions, generally abandoning the old methods of teaching, make it possible to achieve effective results through new innovative methods. The central problem of organizing foreign language education in higher educational institutions is the issue of determining the appropriate educational content. On the one hand, the goal is determined by the objective needs of the majority, represents the social order, on the other hand, it provides the content of education and its organization. Strengthening of communicative aspects in this direction is reflected in changing educational goals and teaching content in philological or non-philological educational institutions. It is not limited to knowledge of the language, but effective use of it in real communication, acquisition of practical language skills and competences and, as a result, development of "speaking". It should be noted that at the same time, the competence approach is widely applied in the teaching process of all subjects, because it is not enough to give the student knowledge and skills in the subject, but the priority is the need to be able to apply the acquired knowledge in practice. In this case, it is permissible to get acquainted with the existing views and opinions about the communicative approach that we have determined for the research.

According to the conducted scientific studies, the competence approach in the education system is divided into three stages. In the first stage - (1960-70), education based on the competence approach appeared as an educational direction in the United States of America. Its first idea was taken from the generative grammar of N. Chomsky, who in 1965 expressed the opinion that "there is a fundamental difference between language competence or knowledge and the application or actual use of a language". According to the scientist, this process represents communicative activity, the main focus of which is the formation of the student's ability to express information related to everyday life in his speech [2]. In the second stage - (1970-90), social competence and personal competence were created in the processes of learning a foreign

language, management, communication. In the third stage - by the Council of Europe (1990), strategic, social, sociolinguistic, language and educational-cognitive competencies were developed. Researchers N.V. Kuzmina, A.K.Markova, L.A.Petrovskaya, [3,4,5] put various competencies into practice. Also, in the development of education based on the competence approach, the UNESCO international organization has determined that several important competencies have their own characteristics. The issue of learning foreign languages based on the competency-based approach is one of the main issues awaiting a solution in the West at the beginning of the 20th century and has been studied by a number of scientists in their scientific works.

Competency based approach is characterized by increasing complexity and dynamics in life situations. This means that people must be able to live and work in a complex dynamic environment. Education teaches people ways to help them solve new problems in unfamiliar situations. It is important to educate them about what they will face in the future and how they can apply what they have learned in any situation. Therefore, education aims to enable us to continuously develop various skills. In the competence approach, importance is attached to the formation and learning of communicative competence of a foreign language, the ability to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language with native speakers implies real practical knowledge of a foreign language. "Competency based approach" is the accumulation of knowledge, skills and competences that incorporate the components of communicative competence in order to teach independent communication in a foreign language. A competency-based approach allows students to progress at their own pace based on their ability to acquire a skill or competency, regardless of their environment. This approach is adapted to meet different learning abilities and helps students achieve more effective results. Types of speech activity is as a means of communication, not on the basis of theoretical laws, but on practical learning, using the language in practice. In the process of establishing mutual relations, the expansion of the communication process between the teacher of a foreign language (English) and students increases the quality of language teaching.

Formation of teaching in higher education institutions on the basis of various strategies is important. At the same time, alternative methodological solutions, generally abandoning the old methods of teaching, make it possible to achieve effective results through new innovative methods. The central problem of organizing foreign language education in higher educational institutions is the

issue of determining the appropriate educational content. The goal is determined by objective needs, represents the social order, provides the content of education and its organization. Strengthening of communicative aspects in this direction is reflected in changing educational goals and teaching content in philological or non-philological educational institutions.

References:

1. Anthony.E.M. "Approach, Method, and Technique". ELT Journal. 1963, XVII (2): 63–67.doi:10.1093/elt/XVII.2.63.
2. Hymes, D. H. (1971). On communicative competence. In J. Pride and J. Holmes (Eds.), Sociolinguistics. Penguin, 1972. (Excerpt from the paper published 1971, Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press.).
3. Kuzmina N.V. Professionalizm lichnosti prepodavatelya i mastera proizvodstvennogo obucheniya. M., 1990.
4. Markova A.K. Psixologicheskij analiz professionalnoy kompetentnosti uchitelya / /Sovetskaya pedagogika. 1990. №8.
5. Petrovskaya L.A. Kompetentnost v obshchenii. Sotsialno-psixologicheskij trening – M.: Izd-vo MGU, 1989. – 216 s.

